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Knowledge creation for resilient cyber-socio-technical systems: framing recent research

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Abstract

The term cyber-socio-technical system (CSTC) has been introduced in recent research to emphasize the increasing pervasiveness of the cyber aspect in modern socio-technical systems, with more intelligence and autonomy. Critical infrastructures such as energy, water and transportation systems, as well as essential services like medical services, are examples of these systems. Digital innovation is creating opportunities to improve their resilience to external and internal stressors but also challenges, such as the increased complexity of the analysis due to various dependencies of system functions and changes in the organization of work. Following knowledge management theories, a novel approach leveraging the SECI model by Nonaka has allowed to identify knowledge flow patterns between various working agents (including cyber artifacts) of a CSTC and their influence in the system performance that may affect its resilience.

In this paper, we present a safety perspective of the SECI model that highlights the activities for safety/risk knowledge creation and sharing in a CSTC and use this model to classify research advancements on ICT technology to support such activities.

1. Introduction

Accidents prevention and resilience enhancement plans of an organization succeed from making the best use of its own risk/safety collective knowledge. However, building such knowledge is challenged by the fact that risks are not all quantifiable, given the uncertainty on occurrence and impact of some events, which hinders evidence-based decision making. Qualitative risk assessment may help only to some extent, as it relies on experts' knowledge that is essentially tacit, contextual, experiential and distributed, hence difficult to communicate, combine and generalize [1].

Traditional risk assessment methods, which rely on predefined risk types and historical data, are increasingly insufficient to address the complexity of systems rapidly evolving due to technological advancements and environmental factors. "Cyber-socio-technical system" (CSTC) [2] refers to a socio-technical system in which the integration of cyber components is both significant and desirable, leading to increased intelligence and autonomy. Critical infrastructures, such as energy, water, and transportation systems, as well as essential services like healthcare, exemplify these systems. In these domains, digital innovation plays a crucial role in reducing disruptions, enhancing safety, and adapting to new challenges, such as those related to climate change. For instance, transportation networks are integrating automated systems to monitor and optimize traffic flow, while mitigating risks of disruptions following extreme weather events. Similarly, energy grids are adopting smart technologies to enhance resilience against climate-induced challenges like heatwaves and storms [3]. These advancements aim to make infrastructures more adaptive and capable of facing current and future events for which they should adapt, for example, through self-reconfiguration mechanisms. This will allow them to withstand extreme events, reduce the need for human intervention in emergency situations, and make human work safer.

Knowledge elicitation and management to the aim of safety design, assessment and resilience improvement, are challenging activities in such settings, as these complex systems are characterized by non-linear interactions of the components, either human or cyber-physical, where even the identification of these dependencies may be a hard problem [4,5]. Indeed, since Industry 4.0, smart objects are capable of learning, adapting and acting in the environment by mimic human decision-making and therefore they also have a role in knowledge-based interactions towards co-creation of the safety culture. Moreover, it is well known that the functions and interdependencies in a system can be influenced by the knowledge of processes and the way this knowledge is utilized by agents who have a role in the work (including cyber agents). Misalignments among work

representations by agents may indicate organizational stress that hinders its resilience, as discussed in [6]. While the difference of work-as-imagine with work-as-done has been the focus of most safety science research, the widespread usage of Large Language Model (LLM) chatbots in all kinds of work environments has led to the definition of work-as-large language model (WALL) to characterize their influence in the process [7].

In the initial study of the above-mentioned research [2], a novel approach leveraging the SECI model by Nonaka has allowed to characterize knowledge flow patterns between the various agents of a CSTS and their influence in the system performance, leading to the conceptual framework Work-as-x (WAX). The support of ICT technology to overcome some of the problems in such flows is also interesting to enhance that analysis. In this paper, we present a safety perspective of the SECI model, i.e., the SECI-S model, that highlights the activities for safety/risk knowledge creation and sharing in a CSTC, and we use this model to classify recent research advancements on ICT technology to support such activities.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the concept of safety knowledge. Section 3 illustrates the SECI-S (safety-oriented SECI) model, and Section 4 presents and classifies recent research on ICT for safety knowledge.

2. Safety knowledge

As a preliminary step before discussing the SECI-S classification model, it is essential to clarify that the difference of Knowledge and Information is not uniquely understood in general, although these words usually denote different concepts when referring to practical implementations of digital systems. Indeed, knowledge-based systems incorporate artificial intelligence techniques to organize data in formal (logical) structures that enable some automatic reasoning and learning capability. Conventional information systems usually focus on management of numerical and/or textual data.

Following the description in [8], we adopted the following meaning:

- Information is processed data in context. Information is a collection of data and associated textual material describing a particular object, event, or process.
- Knowledge is information that is organized, conceptualized, linked with pre-existing knowledge and synthesized to enhance comprehension, awareness, or understanding to enable decision making also in similar contexts.

This distinction is in line with the Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom (DIKW) pyramid [9, 10] where sensors, including human perception, are data collectors from reality, and intelligence is defined as actionable knowledge of an organization.

Knowledge is built from Information to handle how questions, e.g., “How” is this information relevant? “How” can we apply the information? Thus, safety information (e.g., an accident report), may differentiate from safety knowledge (e.g., risk awareness) as a result of a cognitive process, which allows filtering of data/information/knowledge towards intelligence for specific decision objectives. Furthermore, social networks contribute to transfer it among different users (individuals or communities). Such a process involves insight and analysis, and it is bi-directional as from the specification of (new) decision objectives, the type of intelligence, knowledge, information and/or the data to be acquired should be identified.

3. Knowledge creation for CSTS resilience

Knowledge creation encompasses something previously unknown by an analyst or a manager, or not thought of (e.g., building knowledge on a new type of emergency), and/or enrichment and evolution of descriptions of safety knowledge, e.g., procedures for risk mitigation after an accident. Furthermore, this process is influenced by the communication/sharing between workers at different levels of the same process (i.e. top managers or blunt-end vs operators or sharp-end and machines), as well as between safety authorities/analysts and operators [2]. This is especially true in the new digitalized setting, where organizations rely on proper functioning of autonomous systems also in safety-critical services such as transportation and emergency management. Thus, the communication pattern in Figure 1 describing the knowledge flow in an organization at the highest level of abstraction, with the roles involved in safety analysis processes, should be instantiated with human and/or cyber components.

Figure 1: Knowledge flow pattern among three categories of agents of an organization

It should be noted that these roles do not correspond to the official jobs in an organization but they are used to distinguish among: who decides what should be done by the process or activity but he/she does not take part in it (blunt-end), who directly executes a process activity (sharp-end) and who analyses a process (can be internal or external to the organization and he/she does not work directly on the process objective). These roles apply to individuals who look at the same process from different perspectives and they are not static but relative to the communication pattern under analysis.

3.1 SECI-S model

Risk information communication in an organization may be examined following knowledge management theories, such as the SECI model by Nonaka [1]. The model represents knowledge creation and sharing as iterations of tacit and explicit knowledge conversions within a single or between different individuals of the organization.

Each iteration distinguishes four types of interactions: socialization, externalization, combination and internalization. Socialization represents the transfer of tacit knowledge between individuals through observation and practice. Externalization means translating tacit knowledge into documents and procedures. Combination allows to reconfigure explicit knowledge through combining and/or categorizing, and, lastly, internalization is an individual process to translate explicit into tacit knowledge for acting. This model is depicted in Figure 2, which displays a SECI model instantiation to risk knowledge creation and sharing. The activities may involve one or more types of agents of Figure 1.

Figure 2: SECI model and activities for safety knowledge building (SECI-S)

When referring to safety knowledge in an organization, these activities are described as follows.

- *Socialization*. This refers to tacit knowledge acquisition by a single individual, when observing others, or interacting with them within a task. Examples of the last include emergency crew operations, squadron flights, operating rooms, etc. In modern teams of human and AI agents [11], teammates may achieve better coordination due to the prediction capability. Thus, safety should consider the fundamental shift from traditional human- machine interactions to processes in which humans and machines share tasks both manually and mentally.

Socialization activities refer to both normal (Safety-II by Hollnagel et al. [12]) and emergency cases. In normal situations, socialization encompasses, for example, direct observation of an analyst on execution of procedures in an organization. In the case of emergencies, blunt-end or sharp-end operators may act by adapting and/or taking initiative to the specific situations, which leads to defining new rules and behavior for safety in the future.

- *Externalization*. This refers to knowledge representation into safety information, such as: accident enquiries/reporting based on experience; risk imagination foresight activities [13]; any type of communication/disclosure about safety at all levels, e.g., how safety normative and procedures are understood and/or indirect indicators of riskawareness and adaptive capacity [14]. Furthermore, debriefing after simulated or realevents is a powerful tool to externalize the knowledge of sharp end operators [15].

In the digitalized industry, new types of uncertainties are being dealt with. Discussions should involve a variety of stakeholders regarding the opportunities and risks posed by new technologies and innovations [5].

- *Combination*. This refers to integration of the information and models to deliver safetyknowledge or to identify risks. In the case of complex socio-technical systems, such integration is not an easy task and might not even be feasible. Perspectives such as technology, software, humans, organizations, safety culture all have a role in accidents prevention studies, and they should not be treated separately [4]. Combining subsystems into a system introduces new paths to hazards that are not apparent when viewing the parts separately. Intercepting these interactions into

analysis models is the challenge of application, by an analyst, of systemic approaches for safety analysis such as STAMP (Systems-Theoretic Accident Model and Processes) defined by Leveson, and FRAM (Functional Resonance Analysis Method) by Hollnagel.

In the modern digital era, three information types are interlinked [16]: Human information (static: role, qualification, experience and dynamic: health, motion, fatigue); Machine information (state information and warnings); Environment information (ambient conditions, resources and workload).

- *Internalization*. These activities refer to introspective cognitive processes for learning (e.g., procedures, from accident reports), adaptation and decision making (e.g., based on acquired information), and identifying opportunities for systems improvement. This is certainly a relevant concern for risk management whose success highly relies on the availability and quality of the information, and of methods for collection and/or automatic interpretation of the information [17].

Multi-perspective knowledge acquisition and combination to the aim of design for safety/resilience or situational awareness is a demanding job and completeness may be unfeasible in a complex system. ICT technology is facilitating in various of the described tasks. The following section presents ICT-based methods and tools usable to lighten obstacles and difficulties to a smooth implementation of the SECI-S model.

3.2 SECI-S model instantiation

A partial account of types of ICT support is provided in Figure 3. A complete state of the art of the methods/tools for the safety knowledge creation process would certainly be of benefit for organizations interested in research/mature technologies that can be used. In this short paper, we limit our analysis to examples retrieved from the recent scientific research literature.

ICT for socialization. This encompasses technology to support activities finalized to safety knowledge acquisition, namely, observation/perception, collaboration and experience with others, where these others may be human and/or virtual agents.

Empowering information from field by an agent is one purpose, that refers to how work is organized (blunt-end perspective), how tasks are performed (sharp-end perspective) and who is performing them (human or machine). Intelligent surveillance systems support better monitor safety in the workplace, identify risks and provide feedback to improve safety procedures [18]. On the other hand, process mining [19] can be a tool for indirect observation. This comprises data science methods and software to gain insights on the process from the analysis of traces (i.e., digital representations of observed behavior). A large body of scientific works in this area describe methods and results to support automatic process comprehension (i.e., WAD representations), conformance checking (i.e., WAI vs WAD representation) and predictive monitoring (i.e., predicting a violation or a critical event before it occurs to support organizations in mitigating its effect) [20].

Healthy Operator 4.0 [21] refers to operators using smart wearable solutions (i.e. wearable trackers for health-related metrics) connected with data analytics software to face potential physical risks (psycho-social health) brought by the new context of Industry 4.0 technologies (e.g. autonomous and collaborative robots, augmented reality and virtual reality, artificial intelligence, IoT etc.). Of course, as a drawback, diminished privacy and increased pressure to prioritize performance must be considered [22].

Strengthen/changing collaboration is another purpose. Virtualization of work has increased in the last years allowing work processes to be decentralized by using geographically dispersed workforce, and flexible working organization [23].

SOCIALIZATION	EXTERNALIZATION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet of Things (IoT) • (Predictive) automatic monitoring • Augmented/Virtual reality • Autonomous system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serious games • Social networks • Explainable AI • Computational creativity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-Learning • Simulation and Training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Intelligence (BI) • Risk ontologies/knowledge graphs • Crowdsourcing • Machine Learning (ML) methods • Events database
INTERNALIZATION	COMBINATION

Figure 3: IT methods and tools to support risk knowledge creation and sharing

Opportunity for safety (e.g., better control) and negative implications of this change (e.g., harm due to increase of temporary jobs; challenges for managing risks in industries with workforce located in countries with different legislations) should be carefully analysed in this new context. Health and safety collaborative apps, virtual and augmented reality are among new opportunities to safety knowledge creation.

ICT for externalization. This encompasses technology to support activities finalized to safety knowledge made explicit through communication and reporting.

New communication tools. Social media allow fast exchanging user-generated content as in the face-to-face speech. As for other types of communication tools for safety-related communication, in a production process, obstacles from the sharp-end may include fear and lack of motivation. Digital gamification can be a viable means to engage workers in safety-relevant knowledge acquisition processes [17]. Social media interconnection with the cyber-physical space of the organization (e.g., human and machine chat-bot communication enforced by generative AI) is another proposal [24] to improve the links between the persons working in the production environment, the manufacturing machines, and the knowledge that is created in the process [7].

Support to safety imagination foresight. Risk foresight in accident prevention methods for safety-critical systems is finalized to the identification of new emergency scenarios. Traditional methods for risk assessment are based on risk types and data on past events, while knowledge of unprecedented hazards, but potentially dangerous for systems and people, is partially solved by machine learning solutions. However, these could be limited by the context variability, the lack of training data, and the lack of explainable arguments for the predictions they make. Scenario imagination by safety managers can be cumbersome and requires both knowledge of the processes (WAD) and creativity. Proactive tools for knowledge elicitation can be built following computational creativity methods [25]. According to these methods, which can be automatized, a new scenario can arise by combination and/or analogy with known facts.

ICT for combination. This encompasses technology to support activities finalized to safety knowledge building based on an integrated processing of documents and/or event data related to risk and safety.

Knowledge representation tools. Ontologies and knowledge graphs enable logical representation of knowledge, in the form of graphs with nodes as entities and links as semantic relations (logical propositions) between entities. These tools allow multi-domain/multi-perspective data/information integration under a semantic structure and enable automatic reasoning to build knowledge-based systems [6]. For example, ontologies to support risk and/or safety data/document harmonization and synthesis are being considered to support systemic studies for resilience of electricity networks [26] given their interdependencies with other infrastructures to manage environmental stressors and cascading effects [27]. A knowledge graph organizing information from large set of safety reports to support safety monitoring and instructing safety interventions is described in [28, 29].

Data analytics/Business intelligence. The potential and effectiveness of modern business intelligence methods is intensely considered in research. These tools are promoted for knowledge democratization of resilience in safety-critical systems [30]. In such areas, the concept of safety intelligence has been introduced referring to the aim to transform raw data and information from incident archives into meaningful information for safety management by means of machine learning methods, which can be visualized in a compact way for decision support [31].

ICT for internalization. This encompasses technology to support cognitive activities in learning/acquisition of skills and competences safety relevant.

Education and training. The benefit of virtual environments for serious gaming supplied through apps and/or virtual and augmented reality to increase safety culture in organizations is described in various scientific papers [32, 33].

Safety assurance of AI. Complex is the problem of training of artificial intelligence agents taking care of data completeness, trust and ethics aspects. This open research problem interlinks (technical) safety assurance methods of automatic systems with resilience engineering techniques and human factors [34].

4. Conclusion

Building and use of risk/safety knowledge for resilience enhancement is a continuous process whose challenges of knowledge reliability, distribution and generalizability could be improved using ICT technology. Various examples of applications and corresponding benefit in each phase of such a process have been provided by the research community.

This article presents a classification of ICT techniques that support the process of safety knowledge creation within an organization. This classification is derived from a state-of-the-art review guided by the SECI-S model, a safety perspective of the SECI model that highlights the activities for safety/risk knowledge creation and sharing in a CSTC. However, the readiness level of the proposed technology, as well as the acceptance and practicability of research approaches in the real world in the short term remain to be clarified. Additionally, the potential changes and new risks introduced by these technologies should be addressed by safety-critical industries and regulators.

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